

Leptocorisa acuta vs *oratorius*: a clarification of rice bug species

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Leptocorisa oratorius (Fabricius) and *L. acuta* (Thunberg) share a common distribution. In Philippine rice fields *L. oratorius* is more abundant than *L. acuta*. The Asian literature mentions *L. acuta* more often than *L. oratorius*. We believe it is difficult for rice entomologists to identify these 2 species. The distinctive characters that distinguish *L. oratorius* and *L. acuta* are in the table. Also see the figure.

Characters that distinguish <i>L. oratorius</i> from <i>L. acuta</i>		
Character	<i>L. oratorius</i>	<i>L. acuta</i>
1. Body length (mm)		
male	19	13
female	18.5	16.32
2. Ventro-lateral spots (abdomen)	Present, usually brown	Absent
3. Pair of dorso-lateral spots on collar	Absent	Present
4. Spot behind compound eye	Present, usually dark brown	Absent
5. Length of pointed paraclypeae (mm)	Long (0.92- 0.96)	Short (0.61 -0.73)
6. Posterior angle of pronotal disc	Bears no black spot	Bears a black spot
7. Color of pronotal disc	Uniformly pale yellow/brown without white margins	Multicolored, with white margins
8. Seventh abdominal tergum of male	Medially convex	Truncate (straight edged)
9. Seventh abdominal sternum of female	Curved to very slightly convex at center	Curved with a small triangular projection
10. Pygophore	Large, rectangular	Small, rounded
11. Genitalia		
<i>Male</i>		
a. Claspers	Curved and tapered along apices	Bifid at apices
b. Left lateral conjunctival appendage	Elongated and curved at base and apex	Reduced to spine-like
c. Frontal conjunctival appendage	Bears two sclerotized plates	Bears one, only the posterior
d. Ventral thecal appendage	Elongated, constricted at center, curved and pointed at base	Curved to shoe-shaped with broad apex
e. Membranous terminal appendage	Bulbous	Reduced to an apophysis
<i>Female</i>		
a. First gonocoxa	Elongated nearly three times as long as broad, with unequally curved sides	Small, with sinuate outer margins and rounded apices, with evenly curved at sides
b. Spermatheca	Thick at midarea, with a median flange, round and coiled tube	Irregular with a median flange and a longcoiled tube

